
RESEARCHER OFFBOARDING CHECKLIST

In order to better reuse a research work it is vital to make associated research data available in better shape. Here is a checklist, covering various aspects of research data management, which can be used at the time of departure of a researcher.

GENERAL

Role: PhD Postdoc Other _____

Supervisor(s):

Research
Group/Lab
Name:

Departure Date:

Project Names:

Research data
will be taken over
by:

DATA STORAGE

Did you store data in group's central storage space?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Path to the storage directory:	
Did you store your data in a specific structure?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Naming convention used for files and folders:	
Did you put a ReadMe file in root directory? (ReadMe file should contain information about: directory structure, path to raw data and processed data, contact information, other useful information applicable to ..)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Documentation provided?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Did you clean your data?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Did you store/provide a list of publications with their DOIs/URLs?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Did you store/provide a list of published datasets with their DOIs/URLs?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Total storage size?	

Did you archive/store following artefacts?		
Type		Location
Publications	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	
Raw data	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	
Processed data	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	
Presentations	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	
Ethical approval documents	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	
Others		

SCRIPTS/SOFTWARE/TOOLS

Which version management tool you used (if any): (GitHub, GitLab, etc):	
Repository URL:	
Did you use group's version management space?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
In case not, did you migrate/upload them to group's space?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Did you store a copy on shared storage space?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Storage location:	
Did you document your scripts/software/tool?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Did you include a ReadMe file for each script/software/tool? (ReadMe file should include information such as, how to run your scripts, what are dependencies etc)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Can users rerun your scripts easily:	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No

DATA DE-IDENTIFICATION

Did your research include sensitive data?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
In case yes, did you de-identified sensitive data before archiving it?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Is data stored at a secure location?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Location of the data:	
Did you handover sensitive data and related information (e.g key codes) to your supervisor?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No

PHYSICAL DATA

Did you store physical data at required storage place:	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Did you provide/create a list of physical data, their storage location and expiry date (if applicable)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Location of the list:	

COMMENTS